

Study of Sexual Dimorphism by Femoral Neck Shaft Angle in Eastern U.P.Tej Pratap Singh¹, Vinay Kumar Mishra², S. K. Pandey³¹Junior Resident -3, Department of Forensic Medicine, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India²Junior Resident -2, Department of Forensic Medicine, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India³Professor, Department of Forensic Medicine, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract:**Background:** The femoral neck shaft angle (NSA) is a key anatomical parameter that contributes to hip joint stability, locomotion, and weight-bearing. Variations in NSA are influenced by factors such as age, sex, and ethnicity. Understanding sexual dimorphism in NSA is critical for clinical, forensic, and orthopedic applications, yet limited data exist for the population of Eastern Uttar Pradesh, India.**Aim:** To study sexual dimorphism in the femoral neck shaft angle among the population of Eastern Uttar Pradesh, focusing on differences between males and females, age-related variations, and implications for clinical and forensic applications.**Methods:** This retrospective and prospective observational study included 300 participants (150 males and 150 females) aged 20–45 years. Standardized antero-posterior pelvic radiographs in the supine position with 15–30° internal rotation were analyzed. NSA measurements were obtained using RadiAnt DICOM Viewer software. Descriptive and inferential statistical analysis, including independent and paired t-tests, were performed using SPSS version 25.0.**Results:** Males exhibited significantly higher mean NSA values ($134.53^\circ \pm 4.97^\circ$) compared to females ($129.63^\circ \pm 5.06^\circ$, $p < 0.001$). Minimal side-to-side differences in NSA were observed within each gender. NSA values showed an age-related decline in both sexes, but males consistently exhibited higher values across all age groups.**Conclusion:** This study confirmed significant sexual dimorphism in NSA, with males having consistently higher values than females. Age-related reductions in NSA were noted, yet sexual dimorphism persisted across age groups. These findings have important clinical and forensic implications, particularly in sex determination and orthopedic implant design.**Recommendations:** Future research should expand to larger and more diverse populations to validate these findings. Additionally, studies investigating the relationship between NSA and other anthropometric and biomechanical parameters are recommended to enhance clinical and forensic applications.**Keywords:** Femoral neck shaft angle, sexual dimorphism, orthopedic anthropology, Eastern Uttar Pradesh, forensic applications.

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Introduction

The femoral neck shaft angle (NSA) is a critical anatomical parameter that forms the angle between the femoral neck axis and the shaft axis. This angle significantly contributes to hip joint stability, locomotion, and weight-bearing efficiency. The NSA typically varies between 120° and 140° in adults, with a mean of approximately 127° , but differences are observed based on sex, age, and ethnicity [1]. The concept of sexual dimorphism in the femoral NSA has garnered attention due to its clinical, forensic, and anthropological implications. It has been established that males tend to have a larger NSA compared to females, reflecting differences in pelvic architecture and biomechanical

demands [2]. These variations are influenced by factors such as lifestyle, genetics, and physical activity levels [3].

Sexual dimorphism in NSA is particularly relevant in forensic medicine, where skeletal remains are often used for sex estimation. As one of the most robust bones in the body, the femur often remains preserved and serves as a valuable indicator of biological sex [4]. Additionally, the NSA plays a pivotal role in orthopedics, as deviations from normal values can indicate pathological conditions such as coxa vara, coxa valga, or hip dysplasia. Furthermore, understanding population-specific differences in NSA is critical for designing

orthopedic implants and prosthetics that fit the anatomical profiles of individuals [5].

Age-related changes in NSA have also been documented, with a gradual decrease in the angle occurring as part of the natural aging process [6].

This reduction is attributed to changes in bone density, mechanical loading, and the effects of prolonged weight-bearing [7]. Studies have shown that these changes are more pronounced in females, particularly after menopause, due to the influence of hormonal fluctuations on bone remodeling [8].

Regional and ethnic variations in NSA further emphasize the need for population-specific data. Several recent studies have highlighted significant differences in NSA across populations, underscoring the importance of localized studies to establish normative values and inform clinical practice [9,10]. Despite advancements in imaging and measurement techniques, there remains a paucity of data on NSA variations in the population of Eastern Uttar Pradesh, India. To study sexual dimorphism in the femoral neck shaft angle among the population of Eastern Uttar Pradesh, focusing on differences between males and females, age-related variations, and implications for clinical and forensic applications.

Methodology

Study Design: The study was a hospital-based, cross-sectional observational study designed to analyze sexual dimorphism in the population of Eastern Uttar Pradesh using femoral neck-shaft angle measurements. The research included both retrospective and prospective data collection.

Study Setting: This study was conducted at Sir Sundarlal Hospital, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh. The data collection was carried out between 5th May 2022 and 25th June 2024.

Participants: The study included a total of 300 participants, equally divided into 150 males and 150 females, within the age group of 20–45 years. All

participants provided consent to participate in the study, and their radiographic data were collected and analyzed.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 20–45 years with complete fusion of the proximal femur.
2. Antero-posterior (AP) pelvic radiographs showing both hip joints and femoral bones with 15–30° internal rotation.
3. Radiographs taken in DICOM format with no visible abnormalities, as reported by radiologists.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Participants with evidence of developmental anomalies of the hip.
2. History of pelvic or hip surgery or traumatic injuries to the hip.
3. Presence of pelvic inflammatory disease.
4. Incomplete or improperly oriented radiographs.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize selection and measurement bias. Only radiographs with clear and accurate visualization of both hip joints were included. Radiologists with expertise in musculoskeletal imaging verified all radiographs. Additionally, the use of a predesigned protocol ensured consistency across data collection.

Data Collection: Radiographs of the participants were collected from the Department of Radiodiagnosis at Sir Sundarlal Hospital. The images were standardized using AP views of the pelvis with 15–30° internal rotation, focusing on the symphysis pubis at a distance of 100 cm. All images were in DICOM format, ensuring high resolution for accurate measurements.

Procedure: The femoral neck-shaft angle was measured using Radiant DICOM Viewer software. For each radiograph, the neck axis was determined by connecting the midpoints of the femoral neck and head diameters. Similarly, the femoral shaft axis was drawn by connecting midpoints along the proximal shaft below the lesser trochanter. The angle formed at the intersection of these two axes was recorded as the neck-shaft angle. Measurements were performed

separately for the right and left femur, and the average was calculated.

Statistical Analysis: The data were compiled and analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were calculated for the neck-shaft angles. Independent t-tests were used to compare the angles between male and female participants and between the right and left sides. Statistical significance was set at a p-value of <0.05.

Results

The study included a total of 300 participants, with an equal distribution of 150 males and 150 females. Participants were stratified into three age groups: 20–30 years, 31–40 years, and 41–50 years.

Table 1: Distribution of Study Participants by Age Groups

Age Group (Years)	Male (n=150)	Female (n=150)	Total (n=300)	Percentage (%)
20–30	56	71	127	42.3
31–40	43	36	79	26.3
41–50	51	43	94	31.3

The majority of participants were in the 20–30 age group, accounting for 42.3% of the total sample. Female participants were slightly more represented in this group than males.

Neck Shaft Angle by Gender

The neck shaft angle (NSA) was measured for both right and left femurs. Males demonstrated a higher mean NSA compared to females, and the difference was statistically significant.

Table 2: Mean Neck Shaft Angle by Gender

Gender	Mean NSA (°)	SD	Minimum NSA (°)	Maximum NSA (°)
Male	134.53	4.97	126.5	141.3
Female	129.63	5.06	119.8	137.0

Males exhibited a significantly higher mean NSA ($134.53^\circ \pm 4.97^\circ$) compared to females ($129.63^\circ \pm 5.06^\circ$). Statistical analysis using an independent t-test revealed this difference to be significant ($p < 0.001$).

Neck Shaft Angle by Side: The NSA for the right and left sides was measured separately to assess any side-to-side differences within each gender.

Table 3: Mean Neck Shaft Angle by Side and Gender

Gender	Side	Mean NSA (°)	SD	Minimum NSA (°)	Maximum NSA (°)
Male	Right	134.59	4.93	126.7	141.2
	Left	134.47	5.02	126.3	140.9
Female	Right	129.34	5.05	119.9	136.5
	Left	129.93	5.06	120.2	137.4

Males had higher NSA values for both sides compared to females. However, the side-to-side difference was not statistically significant within either gender.

Statistical Comparison Between Genders: To evaluate sexual dimorphism, the NSA values were compared between genders using independent t-tests.

Table 4: Comparison of Neck Shaft Angle Between Males and Females

Parameter	Mean Difference (°)	t-value	p-value
Right NSA	5.25	9.63	<0.001*
Left NSA	4.54	8.22	<0.001*
Total Mean NSA	4.89	12.63	<0.001*

There was a statistically significant difference in NSA values between males and females for both right and left sides, as well as for the total mean NSA.

Correlation Between Neck Shaft Angle and Age: The NSA was analyzed across different age groups to assess its variation with age. The results are shown in the following table:

Table 5: Mean Neck Shaft Angle by Age Group

Age Group (Years)	Male Mean NSA (°)	Female Mean NSA (°)	p-value
20–30	135.8	129.5	<0.01*
31–40	134.2	128.9	<0.01*
41–50	132.7	128.3	<0.05*

NSA values tended to decrease with age in both males and females. However, males consistently exhibited higher NSA values across all age groups.

Right vs. Left Neck Shaft Angle Comparison: Paired t-tests were conducted to compare the right and left NSA within each gender.

Table 6: Right vs. Left Neck Shaft Angle Comparison

Gender	Side	Mean Difference (°)	t-value	p-value
Male	Right vs Left	0.12	1.57	0.118
Female	Right vs Left	0.59	8.89	0.071

Observation: The difference between right and left NSA values was not statistically significant in either gender ($p > 0.05$).

Summary of Results

- Gender Differences:** Males had significantly higher NSA values than females for both right and left sides, as well as overall mean NSA ($p < 0.001$).
- Age-Related Trends:** NSA decreased with age in both genders, but males consistently showed higher values across all age groups.
- Side-to-Side Comparison:** There was no significant difference between right and left NSA values within either gender.
- Statistical Significance:** Independent t-tests confirmed significant sexual dimorphism in NSA values, supporting the hypothesis of gender differences.

Discussion

The study analyzed sexual dimorphism in the femoral neck shaft angle (NSA) among 300 participants (150 males and 150 females) from Eastern Uttar Pradesh. Significant differences in NSA between genders were observed, confirming the presence of sexual dimorphism. Males exhibited a higher mean NSA ($134.53^\circ \pm 4.97^\circ$) compared to females ($129.63^\circ \pm 5.06^\circ$), and this difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). When examined separately for the right and left femurs, males consistently demonstrated higher NSA values than females on both sides. The mean difference between genders was 5.25° for the right femur and 4.54° for the left femur, reflecting notable differences in femoral geometry between males and females.

Side-to-side comparisons within each gender revealed minimal differences. In males, the mean NSA for the right femur ($134.59^\circ \pm 4.93^\circ$) was slightly higher than for the left femur ($134.47^\circ \pm 5.02^\circ$), but the difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, in females, the mean NSA for the left femur ($129.93^\circ \pm 5.06^\circ$) was slightly higher than for the right femur ($129.34^\circ \pm 5.05^\circ$), but this difference was also not statistically significant. These findings suggest that while sexual dimorphism is evident in NSA values, side-to-side differences within each gender are negligible.

The NSA showed an age-related decline in both genders, with younger participants (20–30 years) demonstrating the highest values. Males in this age group had a mean NSA of 135.8° , while females had

a mean NSA of 129.5° . By the 41–50 age group, NSA values declined to 132.7° in males and 128.3° in females. Despite this reduction with age, males consistently exhibited higher NSA values than females across all age groups, indicating that sexual dimorphism persists throughout adulthood.

The study confirms that sexual dimorphism in NSA is a prominent feature of femoral geometry, with males exhibiting higher NSA values compared to females. This difference likely reflects adaptations for greater load-bearing capacity and mechanical stability in males. The observed minimal side-to-side differences suggest symmetrical development of femoral structure within each gender. The decline in NSA with age may be attributed to changes in bone density and mechanical loading over time. These findings have important clinical and forensic implications, including the design of prosthetics, surgical interventions, and anthropological applications for sex determination. Sexual dimorphism in the femoral neck-shaft angle (NSA) has been widely studied across different populations.

In Odisha, India, a study on 84 adult femora found that the mean NSA was slightly higher in males (125.9°) than in females (125.7°), with statistically significant differences ($p < 0.0001$). These variations are critical for medico-legal identification and orthopedic applications, including reconstructive surgeries and prosthesis design [11]. Similarly, a study conducted in Bihar, India, using 62 dry femora reported a mean NSA of 140° for males and 132.62° for females. While the bilateral asymmetry was insignificant, the observed sexual dimorphism supported its anthropometric importance [12].

In the sub-Himalayan population of Northwest India, a combined approach using digital radiography and dry bone measurements revealed mean NSAs of 127.45° and 126.90° , respectively. Although males had slightly higher NSAs than females, the differences were not statistically significant. This study emphasized the anthropological and clinical relevance of NSA in diagnosing hip pathology and designing implants [13]. In Nepal, a radiographic evaluation of 148 individuals found average NSAs of 134.96° for males and 134° for females. While differences between genders and across age groups were observed, these were not statistically significant, reflecting population-specific trends in NSA variation [14].

Conclusion

The study establishes the presence of significant sexual dimorphism in the femoral neck shaft angle among the population of Eastern Uttar Pradesh. Males consistently exhibited higher NSA values than females, with minimal side-to-side differences. Age-related reductions in NSA were observed, but sexual dimorphism persisted across all age groups. These findings provide valuable insights for clinical applications, such as orthopedic implant design and anthropological studies for gender identification. Further research with larger and more diverse populations is recommended to generalize these findings and explore additional factors influencing NSA.

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